

ISic4413

Epitaph for Kallo

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2016 visited museum

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

Tomb 27 of the necropolis in contrada Cardusa

Coordinates

38.065190, 15.114380

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Tripi, Museo Archeologico Santi Furnari di Tripi, inventory ME23436

Physical Description

Two joining fragments of a stele of the local stone, forming part of an eptymbion ('type B')

Dimensions

Height 120 cm

Width 29.5 cm

Depth 15.5 cm

Layout

Single line of Greek letters filling the width of the stone

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Broad simple letters: kappa has short, approximately equal arms; alpha is broad with broken bar; omicron is small and mid-line; sigma has horizontal top and bottom strokes.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: NA mm

Text

1. Καλλοῦς

Apparatus

text of Sofia 2018

Translation (en)

(Tomb) of Kallo

Commentary

The name Καλλῶ [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?namenoaccents=%CE%9A%CE%91%CE%9B%CE%9B%CE%A9] is not attested in

Sicily, but is reasonably widespread, including western Greece.

Digital identifiers:

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4413>

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Bibliography

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